

The Impact of Data Augmentation and Oversampling on Cultural Competence in Social Robotics

1st Enzo Ubaldo Petrocco
DIBRIS
University of Genoa
Genoa, Italy
enzoubaldo.petrocco@edu.unige.it

2nd Antonio Sgorbissa
DIBRIS
University of Genoa
Genoa, Italy
antonio.sgorbissa@unige.it

3rd Luca Oneto
DIBRIS
University of Genoa
Genoa, Italy
luca.oneto@unige.it

Abstract—In recent years, as robots have gained popularity, concerns have raised about their ethical and social impacts, in particular, the need for robots to be culturally competent (adaptable to different cultures). This issue is especially pronounced in autonomous systems that use machine learning (ML), as these systems reflect biases in the training data, leading to the underrepresentation of certain cultures. To tackle this, various ML techniques have been explored. In this article, we evaluate the impact of data augmentation (DA) and oversampling (OS) on enhancing the cultural competence of ML models in two social robotics use cases.

Index Terms—Social Robots, Cultural Competence, Data Augmentation, Oversampling

I. INTRODUCTION

Social robotics, the study of how robots interact verbally and non verbally with humans in various environments [6, 13], is gaining increasing attention. As this technology advances, its social and ethical implications must be addressed, particularly the need for robots to be culturally competent [1], namely adapt to different cultures.

Research has demonstrated that culture influences human perception and behavior, prompting studies specifically on robots [1, 12, 16], which has led to the development of culturally competent robots [1]–[3, 9].

However, complex tasks increasingly depend on machine learning (ML). While cultural competence has been explored in ML [4, 11, 18], the challenge of culturally imbalanced data [14] is often overlooked.

A prior study [10] found that ML models trained primarily on one culture typically perform poorly on others, revealing cultural incompetence due to an underrepresentation issue [17]. Traditional methods to address this, such as oversampling (OS) and data augmentation (DA) [15], are tested in this work.

II. METHODOLOGY

Robotics applications often involve computer vision tasks such as image recognition [7], with binary classification being one of the simplest. In this problem, an image is classified as belonging to one of two classes. Examples include the 'LAMP' problem, determining whether a lamp is on or off

from an image, and the 'CARPET' problem, identifying if a carpet is present in room photos. Cultural factors influence these images, so we gathered a LAMP dataset with Chinese, French, and Turkish images, and a CARPET dataset with Indian, Japanese, and Scandinavian images.

To solve binary image classification, researchers often use ML. In the classical ML framework [5], a dataset $D_n = (x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$ is used to learn a function $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ that approximates $P(\mathcal{Y}|\mathcal{X})$, where \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} are the input and output spaces.

Since learning involves hyperparameters, model selection [8] is essential. This involves splitting the dataset into training (\mathcal{L}), validation (\mathcal{V}), and test (\mathcal{T}) sets, training the model on \mathcal{L} , selecting hyperparameters using \mathcal{V} , and evaluating performance on \mathcal{T} . The process is repeated n_r times for robustness. The error rate ($\text{ERR} = \frac{n_m}{n_{tot}}$) is used for binary classification, where n_m is the number of errors, and n_{tot} is the total samples.

In our culturally competent framework, models are tested separately for each culture using subsamples \mathcal{L}^C , \mathcal{V}^C , and \mathcal{T}^C for each culture C . We compute the error rate for each culture (ERR^C) and assess cultural incompetence using the CIC metric [10]. With two metrics (CIC and ERR), we can't optimize both simultaneously. We select the best model by choosing those with ERR less than $\text{ERR}(\tau + 1)$, where $\tau = 10\%$, and then pick the one with the highest CIC.

To simulate data scarcity, reduced subsets of \mathcal{L}^C and \mathcal{V}^C are used for all cultures except one, which is treated as the majority, while others are considered minorities. For instance, an ML model trained mainly on Chinese lamps may perform well but struggle with French lamps, reducing the robot's effectiveness in a French household.

Our contribution is applying OS and DA to vary the effect on cultural incompetence. OS balances the dataset by cloning minority culture images in learning and validation sets until each culture has an equal number of samples. DA includes transformations like Horizontal Flip, Rotation, Gaussian Noise, Brightness, and Zoom, in the learning phase directly in the model for preventing overfitting. Gaussian Noise and Zoom are controlled by a parameter g .

Algorithm	Majority	ERR ^{Chin.}	ERR ^{Fren.}	ERR ^{Turk.}	CIC
NODA, No OS	Chin.	11.8%	15.4%	31.0%	7.6%
	Fren.	19.0%	9.8%	31.3%	10.3%
	Turk.	30.1%	28.3%	9.0%	13.5%
DA, No OS	Chin.	10.7% (+1.1%)	16.2% (-0.8%)	22.5% (+8.5%)	5.8% (+1.8%)
	Fren.	17.8% (+1.2%)	10.5% (-0.7%)	29.3% (+2.0%)	8.7% (+1.6%)
	Turk.	25.8% (+4.3%)	25.6% (+2.7%)	11.9% (-2.9%)	9.2% (+4.3%)
NODA, OS	Chin.	10.3% (+1.5%)	16.1% (-0.7%)	23.7% (+7.3%)	6.4% (+1.2%)
	Fren.	18.4% (+0.6%)	10.5% (-0.7%)	24.9% (+6.4%)	7.5% (+2.8%)
	Turk.	24.5% (+5.6%)	24.5% (+3.8%)	8.3% (+0.7%)	10.8% (+2.7%)
DA, OS	Chin.	11.0% (+0.8%)	14.0% (+1.4%)	18.2% (+12.8%)	3.4% (+4.2%)
	Fren.	14.4% (+4.6%)	9.0% (+0.8%)	20.0% (+11.3%)	5.4% (+4.9%)
	Turk.	19.0% (+11.1%)	16.5% (+11.9%)	7.0% (+2.0%)	7.2% (+6.3%)

TABLE I: The table displays the ERR^C values for each culture C and the corresponding CIC for the LAMP dataset, for each model associated with a majority culture and its proposed variations.

Algorithm	Majority	ERR ^{Indian}	ERR ^{Japan-}	ERR ^{Scand.}	CIC
NODA, No OS	Indian	14.8%	19.8%	28.1%	6.1%
	Japan.	24.0%	11.4%	35.3%	12.2%
	Scand.	24.0%	18.8%	22.5%	3.0%
DA, No OS	Indian	16.1% (-1.3%)	16.3% (+3.5%)	26.0% (+2.1%)	3.4% (+2.7%)
	Japan.	22.2% (+1.8%)	13.7% (-2.3%)	32.7% (+2.6%)	9.2% (+3.0%)
	Scand.	22.3% (+1.7%)	19.8% (-1.0%)	19.3% (+3.2%)	1.2% (+1.8%)
NODA, OS	Indian	14.0% (+0.8%)	18.6% (+1.2%)	29.3% (-1.2%)	6.5% (-0.4%)
	Japan.	21.7% (+2.3%)	13.3% (-1.9%)	34.5% (+0.8%)	9.8% (+2.4%)
	Scand.	21.2% (+2.8%)	17.7% (+1.1%)	22.2% (+0.3%)	2.7% (+0.3%)
DA, OS	Indian	16.3% (-1.5%)	15.0% (+4.8%)	25.6% (+2.5%)	4.0% (+2.1%)
	Japan.	20.7% (+3.3%)	13.7% (-2.3%)	32.5% (+2.8%)	8.6% (+3.6%)
	Scand.	20.8% (+3.2%)	18.4% (+0.4%)	21.1% (+1.4%)	1.7% (+1.3%)

TABLE II: The table displays the ERR^C values for each culture C and the corresponding CIC for the CARPET dataset, for each model associated with a majority culture and its proposed variations.

III. EXPERIMENTS

We present the results obtained by applying the methodology described in Section II. We used the ResNet50V2 model from the Keras library¹ with pretrained ImageNet weights as the backbone. A GlobalAveragePooling2D layer, a Dropout layer with a rate of 0.4, and a Dense layer were added as the head. Splitting proportions are: 70%,20%,10%, performing $n_r = 10$ repetitions. The learning rate l_r was varied across 0.0001, 0.0005, ..., 0.1, the number of epochs n_e across 10, 15, ..., 30, and the DA gain g across $10^{-4.0}$, $10^{-3.33}$, ..., 1.

Model parameters were learned using the Adam optimizer with Binary Crossentropy as the loss function. To prevent overfitting, we applied ReduceLROnPlateau and Early Stopping. Transfer learning was employed by initially freezing all layers except the head. The layers were then unfrozen, and the learning rate was set to 10^{-5} for fine-tuning.

We conducted experiments using no DA and no OS as the baseline, followed by applying each technique individually or together. The label NODA is used when no DA is applied, while DA is used when standard DA is employed. Tables I and II present results for the LAMP and CARPET datasets, showing errors for each culture and CIC for different combinations of majority culture, OS, and DA. Overall, both ERR and

CIC generally improve with the mitigation methods, except for a slight CIC increase in the CARPET dataset with OS applied to the Indian model. Combining these methods yields the best results, although each method alone also offers improvements.

IV. CONCLUSION

Cultural competence is crucial in social robotics for improving robustness, engagement, and addressing ethical concerns. Although cultural competence has been studied, the effects of ML algorithms and culturally imbalanced datasets are often overlooked. Our previous work highlighted the need to address cultural incompetence due to underrepresentation. This study proposes using OS of minority cultures and DA to adjust data distribution. The results show that these methods are effective across all social robotics binary classification use cases.

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¹https://keras.io/